

“Internet, am I sick?” Lived experiences of Filipino work-from-home millennials with cyberchondria tendencies

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The rapid expansion of online health information has increased opportunities for self-education but has also intensified anxiety for some individuals. Millennials, particularly those working from home, may be especially vulnerable as blurred boundaries between work and personal life encourage constant online engagement. This study explored the lived experiences of Filipino work-from-home millennials with cyberchondria tendencies using a descriptive phenomenological approach. Participants described a recurring cycle consisting of health information exploration, escalation of health-related anxiety, and health belief validation through reassurance seeking, avoidance, or delayed professional consultation. Online searches initially served as attempts to reduce uncertainty but frequently intensified worry, emotional distress, and functional impairment. The findings highlight cyberchondria as a repetitive, self-reinforcing experience shaped by constant internet access and remote working conditions. Recognising this cyclical pattern underscores the need for targeted mental health support and digital literacy interventions for work-from-home populations.

Keywords: cyberchondria; health anxiety; mental health; millennials; remote work

Our hyperconnected world provides unprecedented access to health-related information, yet this accessibility has paradoxically intensified anxiety for some individuals. The rise of cyberchondria, defined as excessive online health information searching associated with heightened anxiety, exemplifies this contradiction (Amini & Ahadzadeh, 2025; Gupta et al., 2023; Vismara et al., 2020). Although advances in medicine and digital technologies have strengthened trust in healthcare systems, the ease of accessing unverified or ambiguous online diagnoses introduces new psychological risks. The inherent uncertainty of self-diagnosis can foster obsessive checking, worry, and panic, particularly when individuals attempt to interpret symptoms without professional guidance (Ahmed & Khan, 2022).

Millennials, defined as those born between 1981 and 1996, occupy a central position within this digital health landscape. As one of the most technologically literate cohorts, they demonstrate high proficiency in navigating online platforms, evaluating information sources, and integrating digital tools into everyday life (Akello, 2024). Educational attainment, socioeconomic factors, and early exposure to digital technologies have enabled millennials to adapt rapidly to evolving online environments. However, digital literacy alone does not protect against the adverse psychological effects of excessive online health seeking. Parsons and Alden (2022) describe the online reassurance paradox; whereby repeated health searches provide temporary relief while ultimately reinforcing anxiety and uncertainty.

Although the precise origins of the term cyberchondria remain unclear, Wall Street Journal writer Ann Carrns is widely credited with its early use (Arsenakis et al., 2021; Khazaal et al., 2021; Powell & Calderon-Smith, 2026), with the concept later defined by Rowe (2021) as the development of extreme and unwarranted anxiety resulting from online medical information searches. Conceptually, the term combines cyber and hypochondriasis, reflecting a contemporary form of health anxiety shaped by constant internet access. As internet use expanded in the early 2000s, cyberchondria gained wider recognition across both academic and public discourse. While it shares features with hypochondriasis or Illness Anxiety Disorder as described in the DSM-5-TR, cyberchondria is distinguished by its emphasis on online checking behaviours rather than clinical reassurance seeking alone.

The widespread shift to remote work since 2020 has further blurred boundaries between professional and personal life, potentially intensifying health related vigilance and anxiety. Shoss (2021) reported that remote work during the COVID-19 pandemic increased stress and self-monitoring, prompting greater reliance on online health information. In the Philippine context, where many millennials live and work within the same physical space, constant connectivity and prolonged internet exposure may heighten vulnerability to cyberchondria by normalising continual symptom monitoring and information seeking.

Supporting this view, Al-Gamal and Lee (2023) observed that poorly regulated online health seeking behaviours can lead to functional impairments, including disruptions in work performance and interpersonal relationships. Similarly, Padagas et al. (2022) found that Filipino millennials with high internet literacy, anxiety sensitivity, and unrestricted access to online health content were more prone to persistent health related rumination. These findings suggest that even digitally competent individuals may struggle to regulate compulsive health searches when uncertainty and emotional distress are present (Beckstein et al., 2021).

Despite increasing empirical attention to cyberchondria, phenomenological research examining how it is experienced in everyday life remains limited, particularly among work from home populations. Existing studies have largely relied on self-report measures or have focused on traditional workplace settings, failing to account for how the integration of home and work environments may intensify

online health seeking behaviours. For example, Özkent et al. (2023) and Nasiri et al. (2023) examined cognitive and metacognitive correlates of cyberchondria but did not explore lived experiences or contextual influences. From a local perspective, Punzalan et al. (2024) investigated cyberchondria among employees in a private institution in Lipa City, yet their findings do not address how remote work arrangements shape daily coping and meaning making processes.

Given the prolonged internet exposure associated with work from home arrangements and the limited phenomenological evidence in this area, further investigation is warranted. The present study therefore employs a descriptive phenomenological design guided by Kelly’s Repertory Grid to capture the lived experiences of Filipino work from home millennials with cyberchondria tendencies. By systematically organising participants’ accounts into experiential patterns, this study aims to provide a nuanced understanding of how cyberchondria is experienced, maintained, and managed within a remote working context. The findings seek to inform more context sensitive interventions for addressing health related anxiety in an increasingly digital and home-based work environment.

METHODS

Design

This study adopted a descriptive phenomenological research design to examine the lived experiences of work from home millennials with cyberchondria tendencies. Grounded in the philosophy of Edmund Husserl, descriptive phenomenology aims to describe how individuals consciously experience a phenomenon, prioritising participants’ own accounts rather than imposing external theoretical interpretations. In the present study, this approach was used to capture how excessive online health searching is experienced and understood within the context of remote work (Pianese et al., 2023). By remaining close to participants’ descriptions, the design allowed for an in-depth exploration of cyberchondria as it unfolds in everyday life.

Selection and study site

The study focused on Filipino millennials, defined as individuals born between 1981 and 1996, who were Filipino citizens or legal residents engaged in work from home or hybrid work arrangements. Eligibility criteria required participants to score between 25 and 60 on the Cyberchondria Severity Scale 12, indicating moderate to high levels of cyberchondria related behaviours. Purposive sampling was initially used to identify participants who met the inclusion criteria, followed by snowball sampling to recruit additional individuals with similar characteristics. This strategy ensured a targeted and information rich sample appropriate for phenomenological inquiry.

The Cyberchondria Severity Scale 12 was used prior to interviews to stratify participants based on cyberchondria severity. Only those within the moderate to high range were included to ensure sufficient depth and relevance of experiential data. Table 1 summarises the demographic and work-related characteristics of the participants, including age, sex, geographic location, and work arrangement.

Table 1

Demographic and work-related characteristics of participants

Participant	Age	Sex	Location	Work Setup
1	34	Female	Outside Metro Manila	Work-from-home
2	39	Female	Outside Metro Manila	Work-from-home
3	29	Female	Within Metro Manila	Hybrid
4	44	Female	Within Metro Manila	Work-from-home
5	44	Male	Within Metro Manila	Work-from-home

Field procedure and data measure

The interview guide and screening tool were reviewed and validated by three professionals prior to participant recruitment. Participants were selected based on the study criteria and their Cyberchondria Severity Scale 12 scores. The Cyberchondria Severity Scale 12, developed by McElroy et al. (2019), is a psychometrically validated unidimensional instrument that measures cyberchondria related behaviours using a 5 point Likert scale ranging from never to always, with total scores between 12 and 60. The instrument demonstrates strong internal consistency, with a Cronbach's alpha of .90, as well as good convergent validity with health anxiety and discriminant validity from general anxiety. In this study, the scale was used solely as a non-diagnostic screening tool.

Interview schedules were arranged according to participants' availability, and all interviews were conducted online. Prior to each interview, participants were provided with a clear explanation of the study's purpose, scope, and procedures, and informed consent was obtained.

Interviews were video recorded with participants' consent, and field notes were taken concurrently. Each interview lasted approximately 40 minutes. Audio visual recordings were transcribed verbatim immediately following completion. A descriptive and inductive approach was employed, incorporating bracketing to minimise researcher bias (Tufford & Newman, 2012) and intersubjectivity to support shared understanding between researchers and participants. The interview protocol consisted of four sections: introductory questions to establish rapport, transition questions to guide discussion flow, key questions addressing cyberchondria experiences, and closing questions. Data collection continued until saturation was reached.

Mode of analysis

Data were collected, transcribed, and analysed by the researchers with guidance from a research professor. Thematic analysis was used to identify patterns and meanings within the data. As described by Sovacool et al. (2022), thematic analysis involves the systematic identification, organisation, and interpretation of recurring themes through careful examination of qualitative material. Significant statements were extracted from transcripts and grouped according to conceptual similarity. These groupings were refined into categories, from which broader themes emerged to represent meaningful behavioural and experiential patterns related to cyberchondria.

In addition, Kelly's Repertory Grid was applied to capture participants' personal constructs and relationships between experiential elements. This technique produces a two-dimensional matrix that illustrates how individuals organise and interpret their experiences (Caputi & Tan, 2020). Methodological triangulation was used to enhance the credibility and coherence of the findings.

Ethical considerations

Ethical safeguards were observed throughout the study. All participants were fully informed about the research and provided written informed consent prior to participation. Participation was voluntary, and individuals were informed of their right to decline questions or withdraw at any point without penalty, recognising the sensitive nature of cyberchondria related experiences.

Interviews were conducted with care and sensitivity, acknowledging that discussions could evoke anxiety or emotional discomfort. Participants were encouraged to pause or take breaks when needed. Following each interview, participants were given the opportunity to reflect, ask questions, and seek clarification regarding the study. They were also offered the option to receive a summary of the findings upon completion. A contact email was provided for follow up questions or additional input.

RESULTS

The data were analysed using thematic analysis, resulting in three interrelated themes that capture the lived experiences of Filipino work from home millennials with cyberchondria tendencies. Together, these themes form a recurring and self-reinforcing cycle characterised by health information exploration, escalating anxiety, and subsequent attempts at validation. Rather than progressing linearly, participants' experiences reflected a repetitive process in which online searching intensified emotional distress and prompted further efforts to confirm or resolve perceived health concerns.

Theme 1: Health information exploration

Health information exploration reflects participants' health checking behaviours and their reliance on online sources when experiencing physical sensations or health related concerns. Participants described a persistent urge to search for medical information, interpret bodily sensations, and cross check content across multiple platforms. The internet was used extensively as a primary means of reducing uncertainty, with participants citing accessibility and familiarity as key reasons for reliance. Searching was rarely confined to a single source, and participants described moving across websites, forums, and social media platforms to obtain accurate and trustworthy information.

A prominent feature of this theme was repetitive and sustained engagement with online health content. Participants reported searching frequently, often daily, to relieve worry and distress. Rather than reducing anxiety, repeated searching contributed to restlessness and heightened concern. Worry functioned as a strategy for anticipating negative outcomes and regaining a sense of control through continued information seeking (Robinson & Smith, 2024). One participant described this pattern clearly: "I look at different websites, forums, Facebook posts, YouTube videos, and I even read the comments. I search almost every day" (P3). Another participant emphasised their preference for sources perceived as authoritative, stating, "It depends on the article or suggestions to read, for example Mayo Clinic, because the people who made that page are medical expert who vlog on social media like Facebook" (P4).

Participants' accounts indicated that uncertainty regarding bodily sensations intensified their concern for personal health and reinforced the need to continue searching. They described moving from one platform to another to cross reference information and confirm perceived accuracy, illustrating excessive online searching as a core feature of cyberchondria.

Alongside frequent searching, participants described actively evaluating the credibility of online health information. Rather than accepting content at face value, they reported verifying sources and prioritising information associated with medical authority or institutional trust. One participant explained, "Before I believe what I read, I check the sources first if doctors really said it or if it was from a renowned hospital" (P2). Another participant described a similar process, stating, "When you discern where the information is coming from, from relevant websites or reliable sources, you can expect that before they post it, it is verified information. They really checked" (P5). A third participant emphasised the personal stakes involved, stating, "Reviews. Yes, I really checked. It is my body. I cannot take any risks" (P3).

These accounts reflect a form of digital health literacy in which participants critically assessed information to manage perceived risk. This pattern aligns with research indicating that individuals with higher digital health literacy are more likely to evaluate source credibility when making health related decisions (Ahmed & Khan, 2022). In this context, verification served both as a protective strategy and as a means of managing anxiety.

Participants also described searching in response to subjective bodily sensations or emotional discomfort rather than confirmed diagnoses. Online searches were often initiated by vague or ambiguous symptoms, driven by curiosity, anxiety, or a need for reassurance. One participant stated, “When I feel something, I go to Google. For example, if my chest hurts, I search for similar symptoms” (P4). Another participant described a similar experience, stating, “Why does it happen every day? What is going on? Then I research” (P3).

This symptom driven searching reflects a personalised and emotionally reactive pathway in which internal sensations prompt repeated cycles of inquiry. Such behaviour is consistent with existing research suggesting that cyberchondria is frequently fuelled by uncertainty and emotional discomfort rather than structured clinical need (Starcevic et al., 2020).

Theme 2: Health anxiety escalation

Health anxiety escalation captures the emotional and psychological consequences of repeated online health information seeking. Participants described how searching intensified worry, fear, and obsessive thinking, significantly affecting their well-being. Anxiety often escalated rapidly following exposure to online content, with participants reporting catastrophic interpretations of symptoms. One participant expressed this fear succinctly: “It is scary. I might die tomorrow because of my symptom” (P5).

Rather than providing reassurance, online searches frequently increased stress and anxiety. Participants described feeling more distressed after searching, particularly when information was ambiguous or lacked professional context. One participant stated, “I searched for the medical term online. It made me feel even more stressed” (P1). Another noted, “I worry if the symptoms I feel are the same as what I saw or read online” (P2). The absence of clear medical validation contributed to uncertainty and amplified distress, consistent with research showing that online health searches can intensify pre-existing anxiety (Vismara et al., 2020).

Overthinking and catastrophic thinking were central features of participants’ experiences. Participants described focusing on worst case scenarios even when symptoms were mild or nonspecific. One participant stated, “You start thinking immediately if you have a tumour, even if it is just a simple headache” (P3). This tendency reflects cognitive biases commonly associated with anxiety, where ambiguous information is interpreted negatively.

To cope with distress, some participants described using distraction strategies to avoid dwelling on online information. One participant explained, “I try to fill my thoughts with happy things instead of dwelling on what I see online. I do not pay attention to it anymore” (P2). Another stated, “When I focus on work, I do not notice the pain as much. But when I stop, I suddenly feel it again” (P3). Similarly, another participant described using entertainment as a coping strategy, stating, “I watch K dramas for distraction. That is why I love staying at home” (P3).

Participants also described panic like responses associated with excessive searching. Although not always meeting clinical criteria for panic attacks, these experiences involved somatic symptoms such as rapid heartbeat and intense fear. One participant stated, “My heartbeat becomes fast. It makes me panic, but I still continue to search” (P3). Another noted, “Sometimes it really scares you when you see research or information online” (P3). These accounts suggest that excessive online searching may trigger panic like responses distinct from typical internet use (Heinen et al., 2021).

Sleep disturbance emerged as a further consequence of ongoing searching and anxiety. Participants reported difficulty disengaging from online content, leading to delayed sleep and exhaustion. One

participant stated, “Even when I put my phone down to sleep, I pick it up again and search. I have trouble falling asleep” (P1). Another noted, “As much as I want to sleep, I cannot seem to do so” (P2). Sleep deprivation may further exacerbate anxiety, increasing vulnerability to continued searching (Uccella et al., 2023).

Participants also described the impact of cyberchondria on interpersonal relationships. Persistent worry and preoccupation with health concerns affected daily functioning and strained family relationships. One participant stated, “It does not affect my work, but it affects my daily tasks and my relationship with my family” (P1). Another explained, “If it affects my job, it affects my family. It affects many areas” (P5). These accounts illustrate how cyberchondria extends beyond individual distress to affect broader social functioning.

Health-related anxiety was not limited to participants’ own well-being but extended to concerns about loved ones. Participants described searching excessively for information related to family members’ health, reflecting heightened responsibility and fear. One participant stated, “Even when my daughters’ paediatrician says something, I still look it up online because I am afraid there is an undetected illness” (P1). This reflects the intrusive and pervasive nature of cyberchondria and its relational consequences.

Theme 3: Health belief validation

Health belief validation describes how participants attempted to confirm, manage, or resolve health concerns following online searches. Participants’ responses varied between avoidance of professional care and active reassurance seeking.

Some participants delayed or avoided consulting medical professionals, citing financial constraints, perceived self-efficacy, or preference for self-management. One participant stated, “I just use the internet. It is expensive to go to the doctor” (P3). Another explained, “I delayed consulting because I felt confident I could control it” (P5). These accounts suggest that online information sometimes reinforced a sense of control that reduced perceived need for professional consultation.

Participants also described relying on home remedies as accessible alternatives to medical care. Cultural norms and familiarity with traditional practices influenced these choices. One participant stated, “We are Asians, so using home remedies is acceptable” (P5). Another described using ginger, vinegar, and topical remedies learned through family practices (P3). Others reported searching online for traditional or alternative treatments (P2).

In contrast, some participants sought professional help after engaging in online searching. These participants described using online information as a preliminary step before consulting healthcare providers or trusted medical contacts. One participant stated, “I have a sister who is a medical technologist, so I always check with her” (P2). Another explained, “If I feel my life is threatened, I would rather talk to a medical professional than read online” (P5). A further participant stated, “The internet helps me understand what I might be feeling, but it is still better to seek medical attention” (P4). These behaviours reflect reassurance validation consistent with diagnostic descriptions of illness related anxiety (American Psychiatric Association, 2022).

Conceptual synthesis

Figure 1 presents a conceptual representation of the cyclical process underlying cyberchondria tendencies among Filipino work from home millennials. The cycle begins with health information exploration, progresses to escalating anxiety, and leads to health belief validation through either

care seeking or avoidance. Regardless of outcome, participants returned to renewed searching, reinforcing a repetitive cycle that contributed to sustained psychological distress.

Figure 1

Conceptual representation of the cyclical process underlying cyberchondria tendencies among Filipino work-from-home millennials

DISCUSSION

This study offers an in-depth phenomenological account of how Filipino work from home millennials experience cyberchondria, revealing a self-reinforcing cycle of health information exploration, health anxiety escalation, and health belief validation. Rather than functioning as a linear pathway towards reassurance or resolution, participants' engagement with online health information unfolded as a repetitive process in which attempts to reduce uncertainty frequently intensified distress. This cyclical pattern helps to clarify why cyberchondria persists despite increased access to medical knowledge and highlights the experiential mechanisms through which digital health engagement becomes maladaptive.

Consistent with previous research, participants relied heavily on online searching and cross referencing across multiple platforms as a means of managing uncertainty (Ahmed & Khan, 2022; Parsons & Alden, 2022; Smith et al., 2023). However, the present findings extend existing work by illustrating how this behaviour is experienced subjectively as both reassuring and destabilising. Participants described a persistent tension between trust and doubt, whereby the same practices intended to provide clarity simultaneously generated confusion, fear, and a sense of loss of control. This paradox reflects the online reassurance paradox described by Parsons and Alden (2022), but the phenomenological data presented here illuminate how this paradox is lived in everyday contexts rather than merely inferred from self-report measures.

The escalation of health anxiety observed in this study was marked not only by heightened worry but also by cognitive and physiological responses that disrupted daily functioning. Participants frequently interpreted ambiguous bodily sensations in catastrophic ways, consistent with cognitive models of health anxiety that emphasise attentional bias and negative interpretation of uncertainty. Importantly, these responses were not confined to moments of active searching. Sleep disturbance, rumination, and persistent preoccupation with health concerns extended anxiety beyond the immediate act of online engagement, suggesting that cyberchondria operates as a pervasive psychological process rather than a discrete behaviour. These findings align with prior evidence

linking excessive online health seeking to emotional distress and functional impairment (Al-Gamal & Lee, 2023; Ruckwongpatr et al., 2022; Vismara et al., 2020), while also demonstrating how anxiety becomes embedded within the rhythms of remote working life.

The work from home context emerged as a particularly salient backdrop for these experiences. Constant internet access reduced physical separation between work and personal life, and prolonged periods of solitary screen-based activity appeared to create conditions in which health related rumination could flourish. For participants, the absence of clear temporal or spatial boundaries between professional tasks and personal concerns blurred opportunities for psychological disengagement. This suggests that cyberchondria among remote workers may be shaped not only by individual cognitive vulnerabilities but also by structural features of contemporary work arrangements. By situating cyberchondria within this context, the study advances understanding beyond traditional workplace or clinical settings and highlights how digital labour environments may unintentionally amplify health anxiety.

A further contribution of this study lies in its examination of health belief validation. Participants' responses following online searching were heterogeneous, ranging from avoidance of professional care to active reassurance seeking. Notably, increased access to health information did not consistently translate into timely medical consultation. Financial constraints, confidence in self-diagnosis, and cultural familiarity with home remedies often delayed help seeking, underscoring a complex relationship between digital empowerment and medical disengagement. These findings challenge assumptions that greater health information access necessarily promotes appropriate service utilisation. Instead, online knowledge sometimes reinforced perceived self-sufficiency, even in the presence of significant anxiety.

Cultural context also played an important role in shaping participants' responses. Reliance on home remedies and familial medical advice reflects culturally embedded practices that coexist with digital health engagement. In the Philippine setting, where intergenerational knowledge sharing and resource constraints are common, these practices may offer comfort and familiarity while simultaneously delaying professional intervention (Bautista et al., 2018). This highlights the importance of culturally sensitive approaches to understanding cyberchondria and cautions against overly individualistic interpretations of online health behaviour.

From a theoretical perspective, the findings support conceptualisations of cyberchondria as a dynamic and self-perpetuating process rather than a simple extension of health anxiety. The cyclical model identified in this study integrates behavioural, cognitive, and emotional components, illustrating how reassurance seeking, anxiety escalation, and validation efforts interact over time. This process-oriented understanding aligns with emerging views of cyberchondria as a maladaptive coping strategy that becomes reinforced through repeated exposure to uncertainty and emotional arousal.

In practical terms, the findings underscore the need for interventions that move beyond generic advice to limit internet use. Digital health literacy initiatives should address not only source evaluation but also emotional regulation, uncertainty tolerance, and disengagement strategies. For work from home populations, interventions may need to incorporate boundary management techniques, structured breaks from online searching, and accessible mental health support that acknowledges the unique pressures of remote work (Mirbahaeddin & Chreim, 2023; Perrigino & Raveendhran, 2020; Relajo-Howell et al., 2024). Without such targeted approaches, individuals may remain trapped in cycles of searching and anxiety despite increasing awareness of the risks.

This study contributes nuanced, experience-based insights into cyberchondria among Filipino work from home millennials. By foregrounding lived experience, contextual influences, and cyclical dynamics, it deepens understanding of how digital health engagement can undermine rather than support psychological well-being. These findings provide a foundation for future research and intervention development that is sensitive to both cultural context and evolving work environments.

CONCLUSION

This study provides an experience-based account of how cyberchondria is lived and managed by Filipino work from home millennials, highlighting how online health information becomes embedded in everyday coping rather than functioning as a neutral resource. Participants' accounts illustrate how online searching is often perceived as necessary and protective, even when it generates distress, reinforcing the idea that cyberchondria cannot be reduced to simple overuse or poor judgement. Instead, it reflects a complex interaction between uncertainty, emotional regulation, and digitally mediated self-management.

Several limitations should be acknowledged. The sample was small and predominantly female, which may have limited the range of perspectives captured, particularly in relation to gendered experiences of health anxiety and help seeking. The study also focused on a specific occupational and cultural group, which restricts the generalisability of the findings to other populations, work arrangements, or national contexts. In addition, socio economic factors such as income level, education, and access to healthcare were not examined in depth, despite their likely influence on online health engagement and decisions about professional consultation.

The findings also reflect participants' self-reported experiences and interpretations, which are shaped by recall and personal meaning making. While this is consistent with phenomenological inquiry, it means that behavioural patterns and internet use were not objectively measured. Future research could benefit from integrating qualitative insights with behavioural data to better understand how online exposure, platform use, and searching frequency interact with health anxiety over time.

Despite these limitations, the study underscores the importance of recognising cyberchondria as a persistent and self-reinforcing process rather than a transient response to health concerns. The tendency for participants to delay professional help until symptoms become severe suggests a high threshold for formal support, which may prolong distress and increase functional impairment. Addressing cyberchondria may therefore require interventions that focus not only on information accuracy but also on emotional regulation, uncertainty tolerance, and timely access to psychological support. By situating cyberchondria within the realities of remote work and everyday life, this study offers a foundation for more context sensitive approaches to prevention and intervention.

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